

Changing Cropping Pattern and Its Impacts on Environment: A Geographical Analysis of Amroha District

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Abstract

Agriculture is the basic occupation of the rural population and the main source of livelihood almost 70% population. After 1990 the pattern of cropping has been changed rapidly due to high population growth, urbanisation, industrialization and the demand of the high calories food in the markets. Not only the size of land holdings is reducing but also the dependency of population is increasing on agriculture in rural areas. To fulfill the requirement of the food the farmers are using the chemical fertilizers and pesticides in farming. So the problem of environmental degradation is generating and effecting the agricultural products and human beings. Not only the quality of the food is reducing but also the soil fertility is decreasing day by day. Chemical fertilizers, pesticides and insecticides effected the bio-diversity and created the habitats problems of the birds and animals. Due to high utilisation of the soil in farming the minerals are decreasing rapidly and effecting the agricultural production. Underground water is reducing rapidly due to practice the farming of high watered requirement crops.

Keywords

Cropping Pattern, Environmental Degradation, Production, Productivity, Land Use, Soil Quality, Farming.

Introduction

Environmental degradation is the result of use chemical fertilizers, pesticides and insecticides in agriculture. The pressure of the over population is also responsible to degrade the quality of the environment and responsible to decrease the area of agriculture land. Primary activities impacts the environment through water consumption, soil degradation, green house gas emissions and biodiversity loss. Agriculture is the largest consumer of fresh water, leading to water scarcity and depletion. Runoff from fertilizers and pesticides pollutes rivers and oceans, causing issues like eutrophication. Intensive farming practices can lead to soil erosion, loss of topsoil and reduced soil health. Cleaning of forest and other natural habitats for agriculture leads to a loss of biodiversity and pesticides effected the species. Pesticides can leach through the soil and enter the ground water as well as linger in food products and result in death in humans and non-targeted wildlife. Pollutants from agriculture have a huge effect on water quality.

A growing population has put pressure on land to increase productivity, leading to practices like double or triple cropping on the same piece of land. By using the high field variety seeds the farmers increase the production in agriculture but the soil and the food have lost their quality and generated many human diseases. Conversion of forests or pastures for crops leads to erosion and loss of fertile land. Changing cropping pattern created the problems of environmental pollution, soil and water pollution. It is the result of high input of pesticides and insecticides in cropping. Demand of the food is increasing day by day, so the forest land is converting into the agriculture land.

Objective of study

The following objectives have been selected to complete the present study–

1. To find out the agriculture production and productivity of the study area.
2. To find out the changing cropping pattern of the study area.
3. To find out the changing land use pattern of the study area.
4. To find out the impacts of changing cropping pattern on the environment in the study area.

Review of Literature

Many scholars have completed their researcher work related to the changing cropping pattern and its impacts on environment. They found that high population growth effected the environment and created many problems. Demand of the food is increasing day by day. The agriculture production is increasing by using the chemical fertilizers, pesticides and insecticides. Not only the quality of the food is decreasing but also the quality of soil and environment is also decreasing. The

research has made an attempt to review some research work related to the research problem. Which is present as–

Rejula and Singh (2014) presented a research paper entitled “An Analysis of Changing Land use Pattern and Cropping Pattern in a Scenario of Increasing Food Insecurity in Kerala State.” They found that among the crops banana and rubber showed maximum positive growth in terms of area. Banana is one of the profitable alternate crop opted by the farmers in their paddy fields. Decreasing crop diversity index of the state shows a trend towards specialization. That is farmers of the state are more interested in mono cropping of perennial cash crops which require less labour and more are remunerative as compared to food crops. Mahi and Kumar (2018) presented a research paper entitled “Changing Cropping Pattern in Indian Agriculture.” They observed that 58.7% farmers were engaged in cereal cultivation in 2002-03 which was reduced to 55.1% in 2012-13. They found that during the period 2002-03 to 2012-13 the farmers had changed their crop pattern in order to reap the benefits of economic expansion. Vincent and Manivasagam (2019) presented a research paper entitled “A study on the Shift in Cropping Pattern from Agriculture to Horticulture in Coimbatore District, Tamil Nadu, India.” They discussed that the state Tamil Nadu has also witnessed a shift in cropping pattern towards horticulture. They found that 23.50% farmers shifted their cropping pattern to horticulture during the year 2005-06 followed by 11.50% during 2002-03. They observed from the study nearly 20.84% of the farmers chosen coconut as the sole crop in the place of pulses. The area under horticulture increased to more than 67.35% of the total area among the farmers during 2009-10. However the area under horticulture was 4.5% in 1999-2000 here. Paria, Mishra and Behera (2022) presented a research paper entitled “Climate Change and Transition in Cropping Patterns: District Level Evidence from West Bengal, India.” They analysed that the pattern of crops has been changed in West Bengal due to the demand of the food and the infrastructural change. They found that the share of non-food grains as a percentage of total area cultivated has increased from 2004-05 to 2013-14 in 5 districts of West Bengal. They analysed that the cropping patterns and crop diversification depend on a number of factors such as climate conditions, nature of soil, irrigation facilities, expected profits, land holding size, labour availability, marketing and storing facilities etc. They found that the cereals crops area is decreasing and the other use of land is increasing here. Sangwan and Manisha (2024) analysed the impact of cropping pattern changes on groundwater in Haryana. The goal discovers that groundwater levels have been steadily declining since the green revolution. They state was once able to grow more than only wheat and rice, but that changed when the green revolution brought forth a new approach to farming. Massive groundwater extraction has occurred as a consequence of the state's solitary rice-wheat cultivation pattern. Parthi, Khandave and Shinde (2024) presented a research paper entitled “Impact of Shifts in Cropping Pattern on Socio-Economic Conditions of Farmers.” They analysed that education work experience and annual income play an important role to the improvements in living conditions and standards of farmers due to changes in cropping patterns by farmers. Rupe, Bhosale and Bhosale (2024) analysed agriculture patterns of Maharashtra state and studied about the changing pattern of crops. They found that Maharashtra is primarily a food growing region where 64.7% of the total cropped area consists of food, 7.62% legumes about 3.30% rice and 1.45% pearl millets. Samir (2025) analysed that the cropped area under Himachal Pradesh has witnessed a significant transformation in its cropping pattern over the past few decades. Despite a largely constant net cultivated area, the escalating demand for food, fueled by a burgeoning population and rapid urbanisation has exerted considerable pressure on agriculture land. The area under rice cultivation was 11.50% in 1970-71 it had become 7.03% in 2023-24 in Himachal Pradesh. Pulses area has also declined 4.94% during in this period 1970-71 to 2023-24 in Himachal Pradesh. Gillani and Jan (2025) presented a research paper entitled “Changing Cropping Pattern in Ganderbal district of Jammu and Kashmir: A Temporal Analysis with Crop Ranking Insights.” As a result food grains dominate, occupying over 60% of the total cultivated area. Among cereal crops rice holds the top position closely followed by wheat, while maize ranks third in preference. Cash crops such as potatoes and mustard are significant although fruits have long been cultivated as the primary cash crop and now stand third in terms of total cropped area. Kaur and Sharma (2025) analysed the changing farming patterns in Jagraon block of Ludhiyana district, Punjab. Embracing changing cropping patterns offers numerous advantages for the agricultural sector, the environment and society as a whole. A robust and sustainable food system may be developed with the help of alternative crops by increasing agricultural diversity, mitigating climate change, fostering biodiversity and generating income. Deepak, Upasana, Choudhary and Verma (2025) presented a research paper entitled “Spatial and Temporal Analysis of Cropping Pattern and Intensity in

Chhattisgar, India.” They analysed that the northern hill zone, rice area showed crop growth rate a marginal rise 0.09% maize increased substantially 1.17% while millets -8.00%, gram -3.51% and soyabean -5.77% sharply declined leading to reduce crop diversity. They found that Chhattisgarh is shifting from minor crops to cereals, soyabean and gram showing commercialization but reducing crop-diversity. Sharma and Baidya (2025) analysed the changing cropping pattern of Haryana state. They found that the evolution of cropping patterns in Haryana reflects a dynamic interaction between technological innovation, government policy and environmental constraints. They found that the development of the agriculture in Haryana state is the result of the high yield variety seeds, irrigation facilities and the use of recent technology in agriculture. However this success came at the cost of ecological imbalance, ground water depletion and declining crop diversity. They expansion of wheat and rice cultivation supported by technological advances and government procurement policies has uncouthly enhanced productivity and food security.

Hypothesis

To complete the present study the researcher has formulated the following hypothesis-
1. Agriculture production and productivity is increasing in the study area.
2. Changing cropping pattern of the study area is the result of the high population growth in the study area.
3. Land use pattern has been changed rapidly in the study area.
4. Changing cropping pattern created many environmental problems in the study area.

Methodology

To complete the present study the researcher has used both types of data. Primary data has been collected by using the questionnaire and schedule. Personal interview, field observation and field survey methods has been used to collect the primary data from the study area. Secondary data has been collected from the district statistical magazine Amroha district, research journals, magazines and various websites. Various statistical methods have been used to find out the result related to the research problems. Tabulation and graphical methods have been used here to analyse the result.

Sampling

To complete the present study the researcher has collected 200 sample from the study area by using the randomly sampling method.

Analysis

Agriculture is the basic occupation of the rural population and the main source of livelihood almost 70% population. After 1990 the pattern of cropping has been changed rapidly due to high population growth, urbanisation, industrialization and the demand of the high calories food in the markets. Not only the size of land holdings is reducing but also the dependency of population is increasing on agriculture in rural areas. To fulfill the requirement of the food the farmers are using the chemical fertilizers and pesticides in farming. So the problem of environmental degradation is generating and effecting the agricultural products and human beings. Not only the quality of the food is reducing but also the soil fertility is decreasing day by day. Chemical fertilizers, pesticides and insecticides effected the bio-diversity and created the habitats problems of the birds and animals. Due to high utilisation of the soil in farming the minerals are decreasing rapidly and effecting the agricultural production. Underground water is reducing rapidly due to practice the farming of high watered requirement crops.

Research Problem

Population is increasing rapidly day by day and the pressure of the population is increasing on the agriculture land. The problem of food security, environmental problems, pollution, food quality, employments, fresh water, soil quality, low production and productivity etc. are present here. These problems are obstacles in agriculture development here. Not only the problem of food security is present here but also the overpopulation problem is present here. Mostly farmers do not use the crop rotation pattern in cultivation. So the problems of minerals in soil and underground water depletion is increasing here.

Study Area

To complete the present study the researcher has selected Amroha district. It is situated in western Uttar Pradesh. It is situated in the fertile indo-gangetic plain near the Ganga River. Amroha district is bounded by district Bijnor in North, and bounded by Bulandshahr and Badaun South. It is bounded by Moradabad district in east and bounded by Sambhal district in South East. It is bounded by Meerut and Hapur district in the west. It was the part of district Moradabad before 15 April 1997. It was created by Km. Mayawati the Chief Minister of Uttar Pradesh in 15 April, 1977. First name of this district was Jyotiba Phule Nagar and was latter renamed back to Amroha district in 2012. It has covered 2470 km² geographical area. It is situated between 28°54'N latitude and 78°28' east to 78°39' east longitude. It is separated by the Ganga river in the western part of the Meerut and Hapur district. Its headquarter is situated in Amroha city. It has 4 tehsils, 6 blcoks

and 1133 villages. According to census 2011 it has 18.40 lakh population and density 818 person per km².

Cropping Pattern of The Study Area

India's cropping patterns are defined by 3 main seasons- Kharif, Rabi and Zaid. Cropping patterns refer to how much land is used for different crops at a certain time, how this changes over time and what causes these changes. Cropping pattern are the ways farmers arrange and combine different crops in their field. Cropping patterns depend on factors like that climate, soil, irrigation facilities, farming methods, technologies and available resources. Wheat, rice, maize, sugarcane, pulses and oil seeds cultivation is cultivated in the study area Amroha district.

Table-1
Cropping Pattern of the Study Area Amroha District (Year- 2023-24)

S.No.	Crops	Area in Hectare	Percentage
1.	Rice	28772	12.27
2.	Wheat	92734	39.56
3.	Barley	98	0.04
4.	Millets	0	0.0
5.	Pearl Millets	3624	1.55
6.	Maize	2599	1.11
Total Cereals		127827	54.53
7.	Black Gram	3370	1.44
8.	Green Gram	26	0.01
9.	Lentil	152	0.06
10.	Pea	366	0.16
11.	Pigeon Pea	465	0.20
Total		4379	1.87
12.	Mustard	3698	1.58
Grand Total		135904	57.98
13.	Sugarcane	98505	42.02
Grand Total		234409	100

Source: District Statistical Magazine Amroha District, Year 2024.

According to the above table, the pattern of the crops is as- under cereals crops cultivated area was found 127827 hectare in the study area Amroha district in 2023-24 year. Under the pulses crops area was found 4379 hectare, mustard 3698 hectare and under the sugarcane crop it was found 98505 hectare in 2023-24 in the study area. On the basis of the data of above mentioned crops we found that rice 12.27%, wheat 39.56%, barley 0.04%, pearl millets 1.55% and maize 1.11% share in cereal crops. We found that 1.87% share is under pulses crops in the study area and 1.58% share under the mustard crop in the study area. We found that 42.02% area is under the sugarcane crop here. Sugarcane is the main cash crop in the study area. Pulses and oil seeds crops have very little share in the cropping pattern of the study area. These crops have 1.87% share under the pulses crops and 1.58% share under the oil seed crop.

Changing Cropping Pattern of The Study Area

Due to urbanisation, industrialisation and infrastructure development the land use pattern of Amroha district has been changed rapidly during the period 2000-01 to 2023-24. Over population growth effects on the cropping pattern. The changing cropping pattern of the study area is given below in the table-

Table-2
Changing Cropping Pattern of the Study Area Amroha District (2000-01 to 2023-24)

Sr. No.	Crops	Area in Hectare		Changes in 2000-01 to 2023-24
		2000-01	2023-24	
1.	Rice	29503	28772	731
2.	Wheat	94275	92734	-1541
3.	Barley	109	98	-11
4.	Millets	82	0	-82
5.	Pearl Millets	6260	3624	-2636
6.	Maize	5127	2599	-2528
Total Cereals		135356	127827	-7529
7.	Black Gram	800	3370	2570
8.	Green Gram	36	26	-10
9.	Lentil	293	152	-141
10.	Pea	206	366	60
11.	Pigeon Pea	406	465	59
Total pulses		1741	4379	2638
12.	Mustard	1895	3698	1803
13.	Sugarcane	66208	98505	32297
Grand Total		205200	234409	29209

Source: District Statistical Magazine, Amroha District, Year 2001 & 2024.

On the basis of the data 2000-01 and 2023-24 under the crops area we found that the cropping pattern has been changed during in this period. The area under the cereal crops was 135356 hectare in 2000-01 in Amroha district and it has become 127827 hectare in 2023-24. During in this period 2000-01 to 2023-24 it has decreased 7529 hectare in Amroha district. Pulses crops area was found 1741 hectare in 2000-01 in the study area and it has become 4379 hectare in 2023-24. During in this period it has increased 2638 hectare in the study area. Under the mustard crop was 1895 hectare in the study area and it has become 3698 hectare in 2023-24 in the study area. During in this period it has increased 1803 hectare. Sugarcane crop area was 66208 hectare in 2000-01 in the study area and it has become 98505 hectare in 2023-24 here. During in this period the area under the sugarcane crop has increased 32297 hectare here. On the basis of the above mentioned data we can say that cropping pattern of the study area has been changed during in the period 2000-01 to 2023-24.

Agricultural Production

Agricultural production is depends on the resources of the agriculture technologies, climatic condition, soil fertility, irrigation facilities, transportation facilities, industries and markets etc. After green revolution the production in agriculture has been increased in India and achieved 3rd place in agriculture production in the world. The researcher has made an attempt to analyse the agriculture production and its changes of the study area Amroha district. Which is given below in the table-

Table-3
Changing Agricultural Production in the Study Area Amroha District (Year 2000-01 to 2022-23)

Sr. No.	Crops	Production Per Hectare (in Quintal)		Changes in 2000-01 to 2022-23
		2000-01	2022-23	
1.	Rice	23.30	24.74	1.44
2.	Wheat	29.95	41.14	11.19
3.	Barley	22.79	30.68	7.89
4.	Millets	7.03	15.93	8.90
5.	Pearl Millets	9.01	12.85	3.84
6.	Maize	13.24	24.87	11.63
7.	Black Gram	8.21	7.26	-0.95
8.	Green Gram	3.11	3.85	0.74
9.	Lentil	9.52	6.05	-3.47
10.	Gram	8.55	10.00	1.45
11.	Pea	10.32	15.49	5.17
12.	Pigeon Pea	11.09	12.52	1.43
13.	Mustard	9.68	14.29	4.61
14.	Sugarcane	577.0	831.13	254.13

Source: District Statistical Magazine, Amroha District, Year 2001 & 2024.

In the present study the researcher has analysed the agriculture production of the year 2000-01 and 2022-23 of the Amroha district. Rice crop production was 23.30 quintal per hectare in 2000-01 in the study area and it had become 24.74 quintal per hectare in 2022-23. In this period the production of rice has increased 1.44 quintal per hectare in the study area. Wheat production was 29.95 quintal per hectare in 2000-01 and it had become 41.14 quintal per hectare in 2022-23 in the study area. During in this period the production of wheat has increased 11.19 quintal per hectare. Barley production was 22.79 quintal per hectare in 2000-01 and it had become 30.68 quintal per hectare. During in this period it has increased 7.89 quintal per hectare in the study area. Millets production was 7.03 quintal per hectare in 2000-01 and it had become 15.93 quintal per hectare in 2022-23. During in this period it has increased 8.90 quintal per hectare. The production of pearl millets was found 9.01 quintal per hectare in 2000-01 and it had become 12.85 quintal per hectare in 2022-23. During in this period the production of the pearl millets has increased 3.84 quintal per hectare in the study area. In 2000-01 the maize production was 13.24 quintal per hectare and it had become 24.87 quintal per hectare in 2022-23. During in this period it has been increased 11.63 quintal per hectare. Black Gram production was 8.21 quintal per hectare in 2000-01 and it had become 7.26 quintal per hectare in 2022-23. During in this period it has decreased 0.95 quintal per hectare. Green Gram production was 3.11 quintal per hectare in 2000-01 and it had become 3.85 quintal per hectare. During in this period the production of Green Gram has increased 0.74 quintal per hectare. Lentil production was 9.52 quintal per hectare in 2000-01 and it had become 6.05 quintal per hectare in 2022-23 in the study area. During in this period the production of lentil has been decreased 3.47 quintal per hectare. Gram production was 8.55 quintal in 2000-01 and it had become 10.00 quintal per hectare in 2022-23. During in this period the production of Gram has been increased 1.45 quintal per hectare. Pea production was 10.32 quintal in 2000-01 and it had become 15.49 quintal per hectare in 2022-23. During in this period the production of pea has been increased 5.17 quintal per hectare. Pigeon Pea production was 11.09 quintal in 2000-01 and it had become 12.52 quintal in 2022-23. During in this period the production of pigeon pea has increased 1.43 quintal per hectare. Mustard production was 9.68 quintal per hectare in 2000-01 and it had become 14.29 quintal per hectare in 2022-23. During in this period the production of mustard has been increased 4.61 quintal per hectare. Sugarcane production was 577.0 quintal per hectare in 2000-01 and it had become 831.13 quintal per hectare in 2022-23. During in this period the production of sugarcane has increased 254.13 quintal per hectare in the study area. On the basis of the above analysis we can say that the agriculture production has been increased in the study area. It is the result of the agriculture technologies input in farming. Due to increasing the agriculture production the problem of food security is reducing here.

Cropping Intensity

Cropping intensity refers to the number of times crops are grown and harvested in a given area of land within a year. Cropping intensity is a way to increase crop production from the same piece of land and is defined as the number of crops a farmer grows on the same field in a given agriculture year. The following method has been used to calculate the cropping intensity of the study area–

The cropping intensity of the study area is given below in the table–

Table-4
Changes in Cropping Intensity of the Study Area Amroha District
(Year 2000-01 to 2023-24)

Sr. No.	Blocks	Cropping Intensity in %		Changes in 2000-01 to 2023-24
		2000-01	2023-24	
1.	Amroha	166.34	166.08	-0.26
2.	Joya	165.76	174.46	8.70
3.	Dhanaura	155.22	179.19	23.97
4.	Gajraula	146.39	190.10	43.71
5.	Hasanpur	159.05	167.92	8.87
6.	Gangeshwari	150.82	190.24	39.42
	Mean	157.81	177.35	19.54

Source: District Statistical Magazine District Amroha, Year 2001 & 2024.

According to the above table we found that the cropping intensity was 157.81% in 2000-01 in the study area and it was 177.35% in 2023-24. During in this period it has increased 19.54% in the study area. In 2000-01 the highest cropping intensity was 166.34% in Amroha block and the lowest was 146.39% in Gajraula block. In 2023-24 the highest cropping intensity was 190.24% in Gangeshwari block and

the lowest cropping intensity was found 166.08% in Amroha block in 2023-24. Due to urbanization the cropping intensity of the Amroha block has decreased during in this period 2000-01 to 2023-24.

Land Use Pattern

Land use refers to how human modify and utilize the earth's land surface for specific purposes like agriculture, housing, industry and recreation. Human activities are responsible to change the land use. Humans are also directly impacted by the environmental consequences of these changes. Changing land use pattern of the study area Amroha district is given below in the table–

Table-5
Changing Land use Pattern of the Study Area Amroha District
(Year 2000-01 to 2023-24)

Sr. No.	Land use	Area in Hectare		Changes in 2000-01 to 2023-24
		2000-01	2023-24	
1.	Total reporting area	216787	211777	-5010
2.	Forest area	11858	21001	9143
3.	Cultivable waste land	2884	7739	4855
4.	Current fallow	5258	1527	-3731
5.	Other fallow	2670	138	-2532
6.	Barren and uncultivable land	3568	2684	-884
7.	Land for use other than agriculture	17918	20789	2871
8.	Pasture	192	165	-27
9.	Area of gardens, trees and bushes	1083	1413	330
Total		262218	267233	5015

Source: District Statistical Magazine District Amroha, Year 2001 & 2024.

According to the above table the researcher found that the land use pattern has been changed during in the period 2000-01 to 2023-24. In 2000-01 reporting area was 216787 hectare and it had become 211777 hectare in 2023-24. During in this period total reporting area has decreased 5010 hectare in the study area Amroha district. Forest area was 11858 hectare in 2000-01 and it had become 21001 hectare in 2023-24. During in this period the forest area has increased 9143 hectare in the study area. Cultivable waste land area was 2884 hectare in 2000-01 and it had become 7739 hectare in 2023-24. During in this period it had increased 4855 hectare. Current follow land area was 5258 hectare in 2000-01 and it had become 1527 hectare. During in this period the area under current follow has 3731 hectare. Other follow land area was 2670 hectare in 2000-01 it had become 138 hectare in 2023-24 in the study area. During in this period the area under other follow land has decreased 2532 hectare. Barren and uncultivable land was 3568 hectare in 2000-01 and it had become 2684 hectare. During in this period the area under Barren and uncultivable land has decreased 884 hectare in the study area. Land for use other than agriculture was 17918 hectare in 2000-01 and it had become 20789 hectare in 2023-24. During in this

period it has increased 2871 hectare. Pasture land use 192 hectare in 2000-01 and it had become 165 hectare in 2023-24. During in this period the posture land has decreased 27 hectare in the study area. Area under gardens, trees and bushes was 1083 hectare in 2000-01 and it had become 1413 hectare in 2023-24. During in this period the area under garden, trees and bushes had decreased 330 hectare in the study area. So we can say that the land use pattern has been changed rapidly in the study area.

Sample Survey

To complete the present study the researcher had collected 200 sample to find out the result. On the basis of field survey the researcher has made an attempt to analyse the land holdings size, crops cultivation preference, agriculture technologies input, agriculture production and impacts of changing cropping pattern on environment. The sample based study is given as–

Land Holdings Size

Land holdings size is very small of the farmers in the study area. Mostly farmers have less than 0.5 hectare land holdings. Due to small land holdings size the agriculture technology is not used in cultivation. So the agriculture production effected by the small size of land holdings. The researcher analysed the land holdings size of the selected sample farmers. Which are given below–

Table-6
Land Holdings Size of the Selected Sample Farmers in the Study Area Amroha District (October-2025)

Sr. No.	Size of Land Holdings (in Hectare)	Category of Farmers	No. of Farmers	Percentage
1.	< 0.50	Marginal	90	45.00
2.	0.5 – 1.00	Small	68	34.00
3.	1.00 – 2.00	Medium	27	13.50
4.	2.00 – 4.00	Large	15	7.50
Total			200	100

Source: Computed by the author on the basis of sample survey, October-2025.

On the basis of the sample survey the researcher found that 45% farmers have land holdings size less than 0.50 hectare in the study area. There are 34% farmers have land holdings size 0.50 to 1.00 hectare and 13.50% farmers have land holdings size 1.00 – 2.00 hectare and only 7.50% farmers have land holdings size 2.00 – 4.00 hectare in the study area. Thus we can say that the land holdings size is very small which have farmers in the study area. So the pattern of cropping is changing here due to small size of land holdings.

Applying (Practice) Cropping Pattern-

The researcher has made an attempt to find out the result about the cropping pattern of cultivation of the selected sample farmers. Mostly farmers prefer rice, wheat and sugarcane crops pattern in the study area. The adopted patterns of cropping of the selected farmers are given below in the table-

Table-7
Applying Cropping Pattern of the Selected Farmers in the Study Area Amroha District (October-2025)

Sr.No.	Cropping Pattern	No. of Respondents	Percentage
1.	Rice, Wheat, Sugarcane	70	35.00
2.	Wheat, Sugarcane, Pulses	56	28.00
3.	Rice, Wheat, Peppermint	38	19.00
4.	Maize, Rice, Wheat, Potato	26	13.00
5.	Mustard, Pulses, Pearl Millets	10	5.0
Total		200	100

Source: Computed by the author on the basis of field survey, October-2025.

On the basis of the sample survey the researcher found that rice, wheat and sugarcane cropping pattern is applying here by the 35% farmers in agriculture and 28% farmers prefer the cropping pattern of wheat, sugarcane and pulses. There are 19% farmers prefer the cropping pattern of rice, wheat and peppermint in agriculture and 13% farmers prefer maize, rice, wheat and potato production only 5% farmers prefer the cropping pattern of oil seeds (mustard), pulses and pearl millets in the study area. So we can say that the rice, wheat, sugarcane, potato, peppermint, mustard and maize are the main crops of the study area.

Impacts of Changing Cropping Pattern on Environment

Changing cropping patterns significantly impacts pollution, often increasing water depletion, soil salinization, green house gas emissions and nutrient imbalance especially when shifting to water intensive crops or single crop systems leading to ecological stress, biodiversity loss and greater chemicals inputs but diversified/sustainable pattern can reduce these impacts and improve the health of soil and water. Water depletion is the result of cultivation of water intensive crops like rice and sugarcane. Maximum use of fertilizers is responsible to release more green house gases. Monocultures and intensive farming reduce soil organic matter, deplete micronutrients, increase erosion and disrupt natural nutrient cycles, harming soil health. Over cultivation effects on ecosystems and destroys the habitats.

The use of pesticides, chemical fertilizers and inappropriate irrigation practices has resulted in high levels of nutrient pollution and eutrophication in surface and underground water. Cleaning forests for farmland destroys habitats, reduces biodiversity and alters carbon cycles. In the present study the researcher analysed that there are three main crops rice, sugarcane and peppermint which deplete the underground water rapidly because these crops need intensive water.

Conclusion

Agriculture is the primary activities of the man. Due to high population growth the demand of the food is increasing day by day. To fulfill the requirement of the food the pattern of the agriculture has been changed which generated the problems of environmental degradation. To fulfill the requirement of the food the farmers use

the pesticides, chemical fertilizers, insecticides and high yield variety seeds. Such types of input in agriculture created the problems of pollution, salinity, food quality, water depletion, soil erosion, deforestation etc. The land use pattern has been changed rapidly due to the human activities and the demand of the foods. Total reporting area has decreased 5010 hectare during the period of 2000-01 to 2023-24 in the study area Amroha district, current fallow land decreased 3731 hectare, other fallow land decreased 2532 hectare, barren and uncultivable land decreased 884 hectare and pasture land decreased 27 hectare in the study area during in the period 2000-01 to 2023-24.

Agriculture intensity has been changed in the study area during the period of 2000-01 to 2023-24. It was 157.81% in 2000-01 in the study area and has become 177.35% in 2023-24. Water level is reducing day by day due to practice of high irrigation crops like that rice, sugarcane and peppermint. The cost of the agriculture production is increasing day by day by the lack of canal irrigation facilities. Mostly pumping sets has outed from the irrigation facilities. Summerisable has taken the place of pumping sets in the study area due to depletion the underground water. Marginal farmers are suffering from the irrigation problems in the study area.

Suggestions for the future Study

Changing cropping pattern is the result of the urbanisation, industrialization and high population growth. The area under the pulses crops and oil seeds crops is decreasing in the study area. These crops help in control the underwater depletion, and loss of nutrients in soil. The behaviour of farmers has been changed due to the demand of the foods in the markets. So mostly farmers prefer horticulture than the cereals crops cultivation. The problem of imbalanced ecosystem is generated here. So we need sustainable and integrated farming. The researcher has made an attempt to prepare the suggestion to control the problem of environmental degradation which is generated by the changing of cropping pattern in the study area. Which are as–

1. We should practice of the all types of crops according to the suitable ratio of the healthy environment and apply the pulses and oil seeds crop at 30% area of the cultivation. It will be helpful to control the underground water depletion.
2. Crops rotation system should be followed by the farmers in every year to save the soil fertility and save the nutrients of the soil.
3. Integrated farming should be applied by the farmers to increase the income and the health of the environment.
4. We should control the use of chemical fertilizers to maintain the food quality, soil health, water pollution and nutrients of the soil.
5. Pesticides and insecticides are very harmful to the environment and human beings. We should control on the over use of pesticides in farming.
6. To find to regular production with harming to soil fertility we should use the composting in agriculture and apply the waste management techniques to reduce the dependency on the chemical fertilizers.
7. To recharge the underground water we should develop the rain water harvesting systems in every village and created new ponds for reserve the rainy water.

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